

Ionic Association of Transition Metal Ions with Bicarbonate using Spectrophotometric Method. II. Nickel and Cobalt Bicarbonates in Aqueous and Aqueous Alcohol Mixtures

MOSTAFA M. EMARA*, NAZIK A. FARID**
and
HASSAN A. SHEHATA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
Al-Azhar University, Nasr City,
Cairo, Egypt

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THERMODYNAMICS and dynamics of the CO₂-water system attracted the attention of scientists for many years¹⁻³. The equilibria of this system is represented by a slow hydration equilibria coupled with the more rapid proton transfer steps,

pH of the solution is the determining factor for deciding which of the above reactions predominates in solution.

In the presence of metal ions (Mⁿ⁺) such as Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺ etc. the metal-bicarbonate and metal-carbonate interactions become of great importance and are represented by the equilibria,

Although the latter systems are important in nature, a few systematic studies can be found in literature. Parameters such as pH, temperature, pressure, dielectric constant are very important while carrying out investigation on such systems. In an earlier investigation⁴, we reported results on the thermodynamics of ionic association of Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺ bicarbonates in aqueous solution at various temperatures using spectrophotometric technique. In this paper, direct spectrophotometric measurement of the bicarbonate ion itself in uv range is used to obtain the thermodynamics of ion association constants between the bicarbonate ion and Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ ions in mixed aqueous organic-NaCl solvents at 25°. NaCl was used to fix the ionic strength. Association between Na⁺ and HCO₃⁻ ions was assumed to be negligible.

Fairly good amount of work have been done on the effect of solvent on association of 1:2 and 2:2 salts but a very few on 2:1 salts. For

example, Atkinson *et al.*⁵⁻⁷ examined the association of MnSO₄ and Mn-benzene disulphonic acid (MnBDS) in various water-organic solvent mixture. These particular salts were chosen as good examples of 2:2 electrolytes with MnSO₄ being associated in water (K_A=13) and MnBDS essentially unassociated (K_A<5). Marked deviations from the predictions of simple electrolyte theories were found when higher organic content solvent mixtures were used.

Two spectrophotometric techniques have been used so far while studying ionic association. If the metal ion absorbs in visible or uv direct spectrophotometric measurements are used as in cases of CuSO₄⁸ and Cu-acetate⁹. For other cases where the metal ions or the ligand is not coloured or it does not absorb in uv range, indirect spectrophotometric methods are used¹⁰⁻¹². The importance of spectrophotometric method over other techniques used in studying thermodynamics of ionic association¹³ is that in this case pressure can be varied as a parameter with ease. This method was checked in our earlier paper⁴ by comparing the results of Mn and Zn bicarbonates from the direct spectrophotometric absorption of bicarbonate⁴ to those obtained from the newly developed ion-selective electrode method^{14,15}. The comparison was shown to be very close, which indicates that the present method is useful and can be applied safely.

Experimental

Measurements were made using a Zeiss PMQ2 spectrophotometer equipped with a 1 cm cell. The temperature of the solution was maintained constant (±0.02°) by circulating water through the cell compartment.

All salts and other materials were of B.D.H. reagent grade. All solutions were prepared using deionised water. The exact concentration of stock solutions of Ni(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂, Co(NO₃)₂ and NaHCO₃ were measured using two methods. The EDTA and ion-exchange resin procedures were used and both converged very nicely to the same concentration.

The absorbance of nickel and cobalt bicarbonates, which is formed after mixing the Ni(NO₃)₂ or Co(NO₃)₂ with the NaHCO₃, was obtained by difference at 230 nm and at three different ionic strengths using NaCl solutions.

Optical density (D) was determined using 1 cm cell for the solution (D) and the reference (D'). (metal nitrate + NaCl) was used as the reference and the sample contained NaHCO₃, Co(NO₃)₂ or Ni(NO₃)₂ and NaCl. (D-D') was read directly and the measurements were repeated several times. Duplicate solutions of the sample were measured and the values reported are the average of the two

*Egyptian Petrochemical Research Institute, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt.

readings for each concentration. To check any possible error in the measurements, a series of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solutions were carried out at 230 nm wavelength using an assortment of cells of different pathlengths. The results showed that the optical density over the range in the present work is satisfactory to within 1%. The source used for the uv work was the hydrogen lamp. The cell used was 1 cm length quartz and was soaked in H_2SO_4 overnight, cleaned, and washed with distilled water, acetone, then dried with air before use.

It is important to note that correction was made before preparing the NaHCO_3 solution to account incomplete dissociation of carbonic acid. Thus it is necessary to calculate the amount of bicarbonate formed as

If we take an example to prepare $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ HCO_3^- in the solution,

$$1.7 \times 10^{-4} = X^2 / (a - x)$$

where, $a = [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]$, $X = [\text{H}^+] = [\text{HCO}_3^-]$ and $a = 6.18 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

Thus we started with concentration $6.18 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ NaHCO_3 to yield $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ HCO_3^- . Such correction was taken care of before the preparation itself.

Results and Discussion

The primary aim of this work is to study the effect of medium on the association constant determined spectrophotometrically.

Metal ion bicarbonates have a particular interest both because they are classical cases of 2:1 electrolyte association and because the association can be measured directly by the spectrophotometric technique. Secondly, it is necessary to obtain more precise data under varying conditions so that the apparent difference in K_A determined by the different methods can be examined in detail. Finally, the present work is intended to lay a foundation for the investigation of the same systems at high pressure.

As mentioned earlier, the method consists of measuring the difference in optical density between two solutions, a reference $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ or $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 - \text{NaCl}$ and a sample solution of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ or $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 - \text{NaHCO}_3$ and enough NaCl to maintain constant ionic strength. Let a be the $[\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, b is $[\text{NaHCO}_3]$, c is $[\text{NaCl}]$ and X the $[\text{M}(\text{HCO}_3)_2]$ or ion-pair; the reaction under investigation is represented by the equation,

initially $a \quad b \quad 0$
at equilibrium, $a-x \quad b-x \quad X$

where, S denotes the solvent and X the ion-pair, $(\text{M}(\text{S})_2 \cdot \text{HCO}_3)^+$. Here we adjust the experimental

condition to allow 1:1 ion-pair, i.e. monodentate species.

The stoichiometric association constant (K) is defined as

$$K = \frac{X}{(a-x)(b-x)}$$

If $X \ll (a \text{ or } b)$, then, X^2 can be neglected and

$$K = \frac{X}{ab - x(a+b)}$$

or $\frac{ab}{X} = \frac{1}{K} + (a+b)$

where, the terms have the usual meaning. Since the ion-pair (X) absorbs in the uv range, its value can be obtained using Beer's law directly,

$$A = \epsilon X l$$

where, $A = D - D'$, the difference in optical density between the solution and reference, $\epsilon =$ extinction coefficient, $l =$ cell length = 1 cm, and $X = A/\epsilon l$.

Thus, $\frac{ab\epsilon}{A} = \frac{1}{K} + (a+b)$

Therefore, $\frac{ab}{A} = \frac{1}{K\epsilon} + \frac{(a+b)}{\epsilon}$

Plot of ab/A against $(a+b)$ gives a straight line if the above scheme and approximations are correct.

Fig. 1. Effect of wavelength on the absorbance: (x) 1:1 10^{-4} M mixture, (o) 10^{-4} M NaHCO_3 , and (●) 10^{-4} M $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

The slope of the line will be $1/\epsilon$ and its intercept will be $1/K\epsilon$. Thus both K and ϵ can be calculated.

It is worth showing the absorption spectra of each component separately and that of the mixture. Fig. 1 shows the uv spectra of 10^{-4} M $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, 10^{-4} M NaHCO_3 and 1:1 10^{-4} mixture. It is obvious that the difference between that of the mixture and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ corresponds to the Ni-bicarbonate ion-pair. Therefore, our assumption that $(D-D')$ can be used directly to obtain X is a fair one. Fig. 2 represents samples of the $ab/(D-D')$ against $(a+b)$ in pure H_2O and in mixed methanol-water solvents. All plots are straight lines which indicates the above 1:1 ion-pair formation scheme is reasonable.

Fig. 2. $ab/(D-D')$ vs $(a+b)$ at 25° and $I=0.01$ for (A) $\text{Co}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ in 10% $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (B) $\text{Ni}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ in 5% $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (C) $\text{Ni}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ in H_2O , and (D) $\text{Co}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ in H_2O solvent.

Having calculated the stoichiometric association constant K , we generally like to discard all effects of interactions due to higher ionic strengths. This can be done by calculating the thermodynamic association constant K_A which can be related to K through the mean activity coefficient ($\gamma_{\pm}$) from the relationship,

$$K_A = K/\gamma_{\pm}$$

The mean activity coefficient of the corresponding species is calculated at the various ionic strengths using Davies equation¹⁸,

$$\log \gamma_{\pm} = 0.501 Z^2 \left[\frac{\sqrt{I}}{1+\sqrt{I}} - 0.3 I \right]$$

where, I is the ionic strength and Z the charge of the ion. The values of $\gamma_{\pm}$ for both $\text{Ni}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ and $\text{Co}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ at ionic strengths of 0.001, 0.01 and 0.05 M are 0.859, 0.662 and 0.456, respectively. These values were used to calculate the K_A values at the corresponding ionic strength and a mean value of K_A is then obtained. Table 1 represents all these results for both salts in the three different solvents, H_2O , 5% $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 10% $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It can be seen that the errors in K_A values are always less than 4% which is reasonably good, considering the various assumptions in calculating $\gamma_{\pm}$ in these complex systems.

As pointed out in the introduction, one of the objectives of this paper is to study the effect of solvent on K_A of association of $\text{Ni}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ and $\text{Co}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ as examples of 2:1 electrolytes. In the typical case of MnBDS in methanol-water mixtures, above a mole fraction 0.25 methanol, the $\log K_A$ against $1/D$ plot changes the slope, where D is the dielectric constant. There the Walden product decreases drastically and the mean distance of closest approach increases drastically⁶.

The demonstration that association in 2:2 salts such as MnSO_4 takes place in a stepwise^{16,17} fashion has opened a new phase in the investigation of such systems. The occurrence of step-wise association is caused by strong and selective solvent coordination by one or both of the ions involved in the association.

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIC (K) AND THERMODYNAMIC (K_A) CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS FOR $\text{Ni}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ AND $\text{Co}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$ IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS AT 25°

Solvent	I M/L	$\text{Ni}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$			$\text{Co}(\text{HCO}_3)_2^+$		
		K $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_A $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Av. K_A $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_A $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Av. K_A $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
H_2O	0.001	20.82	24.25	24.90 ± 0.65	20.75	24.17	24.65 ± 0.48
	0.010	16.96	25.60		16.65	25.13	
	0.050	11.45	25.13		11.33	24.86	
5% $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.001	51.28	59.73	61.15 ± 1.42	49.63	57.81	57.92 ± 0.11
	0.010	40.57	61.24		38.44	58.03	
	0.050	28.51	62.57		—	—	
10% $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.001	103.22	120.23	121.24 ± 1.48	102.01	118.82	119.72 ± 0.90
	0.010	79.33	119.76		97.07	119.36	
	0.050	55.91	122.71		54.94	120.58	

It has been demonstrated that the strong solvent specificity noted in the classical measurements is qualitatively explicable¹⁷ in terms of different solvent effects on different steps in the association process. It is then believed¹⁸ that all the following factors must be considered before a quantitative explanation of association in a system such as $MnSO_4-CH_3OH-H_2O$ can be offered: selective solvation of one or both ions, changing availability of a given solvent component due to strong solvent-solvent H-bonding interactions, and coupling of these two preceding factors. In the case of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ion, association with bicarbonate ion in H_2O , 5% $MeOH-H_2O$ and 10% $MeOH-H_2O$ could not be extended to a wider range of solvent mixture. It is of course desirable to carry out the investigation in a wider range but this could not be

Fig 3 $\log K_A$ vs $1/D$ for (○) $Ni(HCO_3)_2$, and (□) $Co(HCO_3)_2$.

done due to the very limited solubility in higher $MeOH$ content. However, the above three solvents allowed a reasonably good test for the solvent effect on K_A , in these two systems as an example for 2 : 1 salts. Fig. 3 show plot of $\log K_A$ vs $1/D$ for Co and Ni bicarbonates at 25° . It is seen that the linear behaviour is very well established in this low CH_3OH content range which agrees very well with data obtained earlier in 2 : 2 salts.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Acid Hydrolysis of Nitrobenzoic Acid Hydrazides

M. H. JAGDALE, A. Y. NIMBALKAR*,
(Miss) J. D. MANE, (Miss) P. A. GIDDE
and
M. D. MALI

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University,
Kolhapur-416 004

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HYDRAZIDES have been hydrolysed in water under acidic, basic and neutral conditions. The detailed paths of the hydrolysis have been established by the use of various mechanistic criteria.

The acid catalysed hydrolysis of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide, *p*-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide and 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide have been investigated at 90° (1-10 M H_2SO_4 , 1-9 M HCl , 1-6 M $HClO_4$). For the same molarity of the acids, the rates in sulphuric acid were found to be greater than those of HCl and $HClO_4$. Detailed kinetics study, using concepts such as ionic strength effect, solvent deuterium isotope effect, Bunnett and Arrhenius parameters showed that the conjugate acid species of the substrate undergo bimolecular nucleophilic attack of a water molecule on the carbonyl carbon of the hydrazide. The neutral species of hydrazide were found to be unreactive towards water as a nucleophile.